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Abstracts

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FunGlass

PASSIVE FILLER LOADED POLYMER DERIVED GLASS/CERAMIC COATINGS ON AISI 441 STAINLESS STEEL SUBSTRATES

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Abstract

This study describes the development of a corrosion resistant environmental barrier coatings on AISI 441 stainless steel substrates. For that purpose, double layer polymer derived ceramic (PDC) coating systems consisting of a bond coat and a top coat were developed. In order to achieve well adherent coatings without failures, stainless steel substrates were cleaned by six different treatments such as ultrasonic vibration cleaning in acetone, sandblasting with glass beads, chemical etching and combination of these methods. It was shown that different cleaning procedures created different size of roughness and there is a relation between surface morphology and the kind of used treatment. The pre-treated substrates were then dip-coated in perhydropolysilazane (PHPS) solution to obtain bond coat. The composite top coatings were prepared from the ceramic matrix forming polysilazane HTT1800 precursor (30 vol. %), ceramic filler particles yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ, 35 vol. %) and commercial glass filler particles G018-281 (35 vol. %). Parameters including mainly volume fractions of the components and pyrolysis temperature were varied to optimize coating systems and to achieve crack-free coatings after thermal conversion. Glass powder was added as a filler material in order to densify the coatings at the temperature of their application, to enhance the cohesion of coatings and to improve their adhesion to the substrate at high temperature. SEM cross sectional analysis revealed that after thermal treatment in air at 850 °C, uniform and crack-free composite coatings on stainless steel with a thickness up to 90µm were prepared. It was also found that ultrasonic cleaning showed the best adhesion of PHPS bond coat to the steel substrate.